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Research Assistant

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Open Science Framework: [x8bm2](https://osf.io/x8bm2)

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Project Role: Project Manager

Domain Expertise: Social sciences - Psychology and cognitive sciences

CURRENT POSITIONS

- Research Assistant, University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy, [Laboratory for research of individual differences - LIRA](#)
- Researcher, [Reason4Health Project](#)

EDUCATION

- Ph.D. Candidate in Psychology, University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy, ongoing

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING PROJECTS

Ongoing

- [Repository of Psychological Instruments in Serbian - REPOPSI](#), Co-founder & Administrator
- [Collaborative Replications and Education Project - CREP](#), Assistant

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING JOURNAL ARTICLES

- Parsons, S., Azevedo, F., Elsherif, M. M., ... **Lazić, A.**, ..., & Aczel, B. (2022). [A community-sourced glossary of open scholarship terms](#). Nature Human Behaviour.

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING CONFERENCE PAPERS

- **Lazić, A.**, Lazarević Lj. B., Purić, D., & Žeželj, I. (2021). [REPOPSI: The open repository of psychological instruments in Serbian](#). Proceedings of the Application of free software and open hardware PSSOH 2020 Conference.

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING TALKS, WORKSHOPS, & BLOGS

- Liu, M., Kalandadze, T., Grinschgl, S., & **Lazić, A.** (2022, June). [Mapping the landscape of the open scholarship literature: themes and developments in the social sciences](#). Hackathon managed at the annual meeting of the Society for the Improvement of Psychological Science, Virtual.
- **Lazić, A.** (2022, April). [REPOPSI: Otvoreni repozitorijum psiholoških instrumenata \[REPOPSI: The open repository of psychological instruments\]](#). Workshop held with the support of the Open Science Community Serbia, Virtual.
- **Lazić, A.** (2021, November). [Ten ways to find Open Access articles](#). Blog post.
- **Lazić, A.**, Lazarević Lj. B., Purić, D., & Žeželj, I. (2021, April). [REPOPSI's perspective on the TRUST principles](#). Invited talk & discussion presented at the Research Data Alliance 17th Plenary Meeting, Virtual.

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING ORG MEMBERSHIPS

- [Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training - FORRT](#), Member
- [Research Data Alliance - RDA](#), Member
- [Collaborative Replications and Education Project - CREP](#), Assistant & Reviewer

LJILJANA B. LAZAREVIĆ, Ph.D.

Senior Research Associate

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Project Role: Expert Project Consultant

Domain Expertise: Social sciences -
Psychology and cognitive sciences

CURRENT POSITIONS

- Senior Research Associate, University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy, [Laboratory for research of individual differences - LIRA](#)
- Researcher, [Reason4Health Project](#)

EDUCATION

- Ph.D. in Psychology, University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy, 2012

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING PROJECTS

Ongoing

- [Repository of Psychological Instruments in Serbian - REPOPSI](#), Co-founder & Supervisor
- [Collaborative Replications and Education Project - CREP](#), Associate Director

Past

- [Boosting EOSC readiness: Creating a scalable model for capacity building in RDM](#)
- [Effect of badges on Availability of Data and Materials](#)
- [Reproducibility project: Psychology](#)
- [Many Labs 5: Testing pre-data collection peer review as an intervention to increase replicability](#)
- [ManyLabs 2 project: Many Labs 2: Investigating Variation in Replicability Across Sample and Setting](#)

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING JOURNAL ARTICLES

- Wagge, J. R., Hurst, M. A., Brandt, M. J., **Lazarevic, Lj. B.** Legate, N., & Grahe, J. E. (2022). [Teaching Research in Principle and in Practice: What Do Psychology Instructors Think of Research Projects in Their Courses?](#). Psychology Learning & Teaching.

- Ebersole, C. R., Mathur, M. B., Baranski, E., ... **Lazarević, Lj. B.**, ..., & Nosek, B. A. (2020). [Many Labs 5: Testing pre-data collection peer review as an intervention to increase replicability](#). Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science.
- Baranski, E., Baskin, E., Coary, S., ... **Lazarević, Lj. B.**, ..., & Zezelj, I. (2020). [Many Labs 5: Registered Replication Report of Shnabel & Nadler. \(2008\). Study 4](#). Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science.
- **Lazarević, Lj. B.**, Puric, D., Zezelj, I., ..., Stojilovic, D. (2020). [Many Labs 5: Registered Replication of LoBue & DeLoache \(2008\)](#). Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science.
- Landy, J. F., Jia, M., Ding, I. L., ... **Lazarević, Lj. B.**, ... Uhlmann, E. L. (2020). [Crowdsourcing hypothesis tests: Making transparent how design choices shape research results](#). Psychological Bulletin.
- Wagge, J. R., Brandt, M. J., **Lazarević, Lj. B.**, ..., & Grahe, J. E. (2019). [Publishing Research with Undergraduate Students via Replication Work: The Collaborative Replications and Education Project](#). Frontiers in Psychology.
- Hu, C-P., Yin, J., Lindenberg, S., ... **Lazarević, Lj. B.**, ..., & IJzerman, H. (2019). [Data from a cross-national project testing principles from social thermoregulation theory](#). Scientific Data.
- Klein, R. A., Vianello, M., Hasselman, F., ... **Lazarević, Lj. B.**, ..., & Nosek, B. A. (2018). [Many labs 2: Investigating variation in replicability across sample and setting](#). Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science.
- **Open Science Collaboration.** (2015). [Estimating the reproducibility of psychological science](#). Science.
- Kidwell, M. C., **Lazarević, Lj. B.**, ..., & Nosek, B. A. (2016). [Badges to acknowledge open practices: A simple, low-cost, effective method for increasing transparency](#). PLoS Biology.

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING CONFERENCE PAPERS

- **Lazarević, Lj. B.** & Knežević, G. (2022). [xSample: A Free, User-friendly App for Collecting Experience Sampling Data](#). Proceedings of the Application of free software and open hardware PSSOH 2021 Conference.
- Lazić, A., **Lazarević Lj. B.**, Purić, D., & Žeželj, I. (2021). [REPOPSI: The open repository of psychological instruments in Serbian](#). Proceedings of the Application of free software and open hardware PSSOH 2020 Conference.
- Purić, D., Žeželj, I., **Lazarević, Lj. B.**, & Knežević, G. (2020). [When do open science practices lead to higher quality data?](#). Proceedings of the Application of free software and open hardware PSSOH 2019 Conference.
- **Lazarević, Lj. B.**, & Žeželj, I. (2019). [How open science norms improve scientific practices](#). Proceedings of the Application of free software and open hardware PSSOH 2018 Conference.

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING TALKS

- **Lazarević, Lj. B.** (2017, November). [Open science challenges - increasing transparency and reproducibility of psychological science](#). Keynote lecture presented at the First Danube Conference for Higher Education, Ulm University, Germany.

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING ORG MEMBERSHIPS

- [Open Science Community Serbia](#), Co-founder
- [Research Data Alliance - RDA](#), Member
- [Collaborative Replications and Education Project - CREP](#), Associate Director

DANKA PURIĆ, Ph.D.

Assistant Professor

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Project Role: Expert Project Consultant

Domain Expertise: Social sciences - Psychology and cognitive sciences

CURRENT POSITIONS

- Assistant Professor, University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy, [Laboratory for research of individual differences - LIRA](#)
- Researcher, [Reason4Health Project](#)

EDUCATION

- Ph.D. in Psychology, University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy, 2014

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING PROJECTS

Ongoing

- [Repository of Psychological Instruments in Serbian - REPOPSI](#), Co-founder & Supervisor
- [Collaborative Replications and Education Project - CREP](#), Executive Reviewer

Past

- [Many Labs 5: Testing pre-data collection peer review as an intervention to increase replicability](#)

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING JOURNAL ARTICLES

- Ebersole, C. R., Mathur, M. B., Baranski, E., ... **Purić, D.**, ..., & Nosek, B. A. (2020). [Many Labs 5: Testing pre-data collection peer review as an intervention to increase replicability](#). *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*.
- Baranski, E., Baskin, E., Coary, S., ... **Purić, D.**, ..., & Žeželj, I. (2020). [Many Labs 5: Registered Replication Report of Shnabel & Nadler. \(2008\). Study 4](#). *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*.
- Lazarevic, Lj. B., **Puric, D.**, Žeželj, I., ..., & Stojilovic, D. (2020). [Many Labs 5:](#)

[Registered Replication of LoBue & DeLoache \(2008\)](#). *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*.

- Landy, J. F., Jia, M., Ding, I. L., ... **Purić, D.**, ..., & Uhlmann, E. L. (2020). [Crowdsourcing hypothesis tests: Making transparent how design choices shape research results](#). *Psychological Bulletin*.

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING CONFERENCE PAPERS

- Lazić, A., Lazarević Lj. B., **Purić, D.**, & Žeželj, I. (2021). [REPOPSI: The open repository of psychological instruments in Serbian](#). Proceedings of the Application of free software and open hardware PSSOH 2020 Conference.
- **Purić, D.**, Žeželj, I., Lazarević, Lj. B., & Knežević, G. (2020). [When do open science practices lead to higher quality data?](#). Proceedings of the Application of free software and open hardware PSSOH 2019 Conference.

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING ORG MEMBERSHIPS

- [Research Data Alliance - RDA](#), Member
- [Collaborative Replications and Education Project - CREP](#), Executive Reviewer

IRIS ŽEŽELJ,

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Associate Professor

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Open Science Framework: [qcsz3](https://osf.io/qcsz3)

Project Role: Expert Project Consultant

Domain Expertise: Social sciences - Psychology and cognitive sciences

CURRENT POSITIONS

- Associate Professor, University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy, [Laboratory for research of individual differences - LIRA](#)
- Principal Investigator, [Reason4Health Project](#)

EDUCATION

- Ph.D. in Psychology, University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy, 2012

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING PROJECTS

Ongoing

- [Repository of Psychological Instruments in Serbian - REPOPSI](#), Co-founder & Supervisor
- [Lira Faces Database](#), Co-founder
- [Collaborative Replications and Education Project - CREP](#), Executive Reviewer

Past

- [Many Labs 5: Testing pre-data collection peer review as an intervention to increase replicability](#)
- [Replications of Important Results in Social Psychology](#)

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING JOURNAL ARTICLES

- Ebersole, C. R., Mathur, M. B., Baranski, E., ... **Žeželj, I.**, ..., & Nosek, B. A. (2020). [Many Labs 5: Testing pre-data collection peer review as an intervention to increase replicability](#). *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*.
- Baranski, E., Baskin, E., Coary, S., ..., & **Žeželj, I.** (2020). [Many Labs 5: Registered Replication Report of Shnabel & Nadler \(2008\), Study 4](#). *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*.

- Lazarevic, Lj. B., Puric, D., **Žeželj, I.**, ..., & Stojilovic, D. (2020). [Many Labs 5: Registered Replication of LoBue & DeLoache \(2008\)](#). Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science.
- Landy, J. F., Jia, M., Ding, I. L., ... **Žeželj, I.**, ..., & Uhlmann, E. L. (2020). [Crowdsourcing hypothesis tests: Making transparent how design choices shape research results](#). Psychological Bulletin.
- **Žeželj, I. L.**, & Jokić, B. R. (2014). [Replication of experiments evaluating impact of psychological distance on moral judgment: \(Eyal, Liberman & Trope, 2008; Gong & Medin, 2012\)](#). Social Psychology.

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING CONFERENCE PAPERS

- Lazić, A., Lazarević Lj. B., Purić, D., & **Žeželj, I.** (2021). [REPOPSI: The open repository of psychological instruments in Serbian](#). Proceedings of the Application of free software and open hardware PSSOH 2020 Conference.
- Purić, D., **Žeželj, I.**, Lazarević, Lj. B., & Knežević, G. (2020). [When do open science practices lead to higher quality data?](#). Proceedings of the Application of free software and open hardware PSSOH 2019 Conference.
- Lazarević, Lj. B., & **Žeželj, I.** (2019). [How open science norms improve scientific practices](#). Proceedings of the Application of free software and open hardware PSSOH 2018 Conference.

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING TALKS

- **Žeželj, I.** (2017, November). [Good scientific practices](#). Keynote lecture presented at the First Danube Conference for Higher Education, Ulm University, Germany.
- **Žeželj, I.** (2017, March). [The new framework for research: How to foster replicability and](#)

[cumulative science](#). Lecture presented at the EASP sponsored Bilateral workshop connecting the social psychology labs at the University of Sarajevo and the University of Belgrade.

- **Žeželj, I.** (2016, December). [Towards a better understanding of science and responsibility](#). Invited panelist at the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) Tools Belgrade Conference.

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING ORG MEMBERSHIPS

- [Research Data Alliance - RDA](#), Member
- [Collaborative Replications and Education Project - CREP](#), Executive Reviewer

OBRAD VUČKOVAC, B.A.

Library Manager

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LinkedIn: [obrad-vuckovac](https://www.linkedin.com/in/obrad-vuckovac)

Project Role: Expert Project Consultant

Domain Expertise: Natural sciences -
Computer and information sciences;
Social Sciences - other social sciences

CURRENT POSITION

- Library Manager, University of Belgrade
[Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences](#)

EDUCATION

- Bachelor of Library and Information Science,
University of Belgrade Faculty of Philology,
2011

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING PROJECTS

Past

- [Boosting EOSC readiness: Creating a scalable model for capacity building in RDM](#)

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING CONFERENCE PAPERS

- Vučkovac, O.** (2020). [Upravljanje istraživačkim podacima: novi vid usluge u bibliotekama naučnoistraživačkih instituta \[Research data management: a new type of service in the research libraries\]](#). Proceedings of the 14th Serbian Library Association Conference.

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING TALKS & WORKSHOPS

- Vučkovac, O.** (2021, November). [Alati za pripremu plana upravljanja istraživačkim podacima \[Tools for preparing Data Management Plans\]](#). Presented at the Open Science Days in Serbia III (DON), Virtual.
- Vučkovac, O.,** Miljković, N., & Ševkušić, M. (2020, July). [Upravljanje otvorenim istraživačkim podacima za istraživače \[Research data management for researchers\]](#). Presented at the workshop at

the Institute for biological research "Siniša Stanković", Virtual.

- Lazarević Lj. B., Ševkušić, M., **Vučkovac, O.**, & Miljković, N. (2020, January). [Implementacija i korišćenje otvorenih istraživačkih podataka za istraživače \[Implementation and usage of open research data for researchers\]](#). Presented at the workshop at the Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad.
- **Vučkovac, O.** (2019, November). [Šta je upravljanje istraživačkim podacima? Zašto je to uopšte važno? \[What is research data management? Why should you care?\]](#). Presented at the PSSOH workshop: Open research data practices for researchers.

OPEN SCIENCE & DATA SHARING ORG MEMBERSHIPS

- [Open Science Community Serbia](#),
Co-founder
- [Research Data Alliance - RDA](#), Member